

New data on Longicorn-beetles of the genus *Dorcadion* Dalman, 1817 (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) from Turkey with descriptions of 3 new species and 4 new subspecies

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Abstract: *Dorcadion* (*Cribridorcadion*) *macropus* Kraatz, 1873, **sp. rest.** is redescribed with lectotype designation and restored as valid species name with 4 synonyms: *obscurans* Pic, 1892 (holotype is figured); *amasinum* Pic, 1898; *atripes* Reitter, 1900 (holotype is figured); *subobesum* Pic, 1942 (syntype female is figured, males were not found). Lectotypes are also designated for *D. (C.) micans* Thomson, 1867 and *D. sericatum* Kraatz, 1873 (a synonym of *D. micans*). Three new species and 4 new subspecies are described: *D. (C.) kartalense* **sp. n.** from Eskisehir prov. (Kartal Gecidi), *D. (C.) paramicans* **sp. n.** from Çorum prov. and north Yozgat prov., *D. (C.) rarepunctatum* **sp. n.** from Kayseri prov. (about 4km westwards Sariz), *D. (C.) paramicans keskiense* **ssp. n.** from Kirikkale prov.(Keskin), *D. (C.) paramicans kalechikense* **ssp. n.** from Ankara prov. (Kozayagi NW Kalecik), *D. (C.) menradi aksarayense* **ssp. n.** from E Aksaray prov.(Gukunkaya) and Konya prov. (Dinek), *D. (C.) pittinorum paraullrichi* **ssp. n.** from Çorum prov. (Sülüklü, north-eastwards Mecitözü and Mecitözü env. *Dorcadion (C.) subvestitum* K. Daniel, 1900 and *D. (C.) niksarensis* Bernhauer & Peks, 2013 are downgraded to subspecies level *Dorcadion (C.) micans subvestitum* K. Daniel, 1900, **stat. nov.** and *D. (C.) tokatense niksarensis* Bernhauer & Peks, 2013, **stat. nov.** and *Dorcadion (C.) tokatense tokatense* Pic, 1901 is accepted. *D. (C.) micans susheriense* Breuning, 1970 (described as *D. sinopense susheriense* Breuning, 1970) and *D. (C.) catenatum subdivisum* Breuning, 1955 are upgraded to species level: *D. (C.) susheriense* Breuning, 1970, **stat. nov.** and *D. (C.) subdivisum* Breuning, 1955, **stat. nov.**

Recently I've received a lot of materials on Turkish *Dorcadion* for study from Mr. W. Heinz (mostly of the very complicated *D. cinerarium*-group). Now all materials are identified, and several series are described as new taxons. Some specimens

from other collections were also used in the article.

Abbreviations of collections:

HNHM - Hungarian Natural History Museum

MD - collection of M. Danilevsky (Moscow)

ML - collection of M. Lazarev (Moscow)

MNHN - Muséum Nationale d'Histoire Naturelle (Paris)

SDEI - Senckenberg Deutsches Entomologisches Institut (Müncheberg, Germany)

WH - collection of W. Heinz (Wald-Michelbach, Germany)

ZIN - Zoological Institute (Sankt-Petersburg)

ZMM - Zoological Museum of Moscow University

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) macropus* Kraatz, 1873, sp. rest.**

Figs 1-11

Dorcadion macropus Kraatz, 1873: 99 - "Amasia (Lederer)", "5¼ - 5¾ lin." [several males].

Dorcadion macropus var. *obscurans* Pic, 1892: 91 [a single female] - "Amasie", "12mm".

Dorcadion amasinum Pic, 1898: 58 [a single female] - "de l'Amasie", "12mm".

Dorcadion sericatum var. *atripes* Reitter, 1900: 88 - "Amasia", "12 mill."

Dorcadion subobesum Pic, 1942: 2 - "Amasia", "11-14 mm".

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) cinerarium, Breuning, 1962: 361, part. (including: *macropus* Kr., *obscurans* Pic, *atripes* Rtt., *amasinum* Pic, *subobesum* Pic).

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) micans micans, Danilevsky, 2010: 250, part.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) macropus, Lazarev, 2011: 263.

Type locality. Turkey: Amasia.

Middle size beetles characterized by very dark legs and antennae - dark-red or totally black; prothorax with large but not pointed lateral tubercles; pronotum with sparse distinct punctation without white central stripe; elytra smooth, without longitudinal furrows; sutural white stripe is accompanied with black stripes; humeral stripes in males and in androchromal females absent; autochromal females can be covered by brown pubescence with more or less distinct pale dorsal elytral stripes; body length of males:

10.0-12.0 mm, width: 3.6-4.8 mm, body length of females: 11.2-13.5 mm, width: 4.8-5.6 mm.

Distribution. Turkey, Amasia province.

Materials. Lectotype (present designation), photo of a male with 4 labels: 1) "Amasia / Leder.", 2) "variet / *macropus* / Kraatz", 3) "Coll. Kraatz", 4) "Syntypus" [red] - (received from Dr. L. Behne - SDEI); paralectotype (present designation), photo of a male with 2 labels: 1) "Coll. Kraatz", 2) "Syntypus" [red] - (received from Dr. L. Behne - SDEI); paralectotype (present designation), photo of a male with 4 labels: 1) "type" [handwriting by M.Pic], 2) "*macropus* / asie mineure", 3) "TYPE" [red], 4) "Museum Paris / Coll. M. Pic" - (received from Dr. G. Tavakilian - MNHN); holotype of *Dorcadion macropus* var. *obscurans* Pic, 1892, photo of a female with 6 labels: 1) white small square, 2) "type" [handwriting by M.Pic], 3) "v. *obscurans*", 4) "*macropus* Kr. / "var amasia" / "de Dr. Kraatz", 5) "TYPE" [red], 6) "Museum Paris / Coll. M. Pic" - (received from Dr. G. Tavakilian - MNHN) [most probably the specimens could be also regarded as a paralectotype of *D. macropus* Kraatz, 1873]; male with goldish ring and 2 labels: 1) "Amasie"; 2) "*Dorcadion* ♂ / *sericatum*. Kryn. / v. *obscurans* Typ. m. / Maurice. Pic. det" - ZMM [the specimen does not belong to the type series, as v. *obscurans* was described after a single female]; holotype of *Dorcadion sericatum* var. *atripes* Reitter, 1900, photo of a female with 6 labels: 1) *D. sericatum* / v. *atripes* m. / 1897, 2) "var. / Amasia", 3) "Coll. Reitter", 4) "Holotypus 1900. / *Dorcadion sericatum* / var. *atripes* / Reitter" [partly red], 5) "*Dorcadion* / *cinerarium* / *macropus* / Kr. / Breuning dét.", 6) "*D. cinerarium* / *macropus* Kr. / det. Breuning 1955" - (received from Dr. O. Merkl - HNHN); syntype of *Dorcadion subobesum* Pic, 1942, female, with 4 labels: 1) white small square, 2) "*subobesum* / n. sp." 3) "TYPE" [red], 4) "Museum Paris / Coll. M. Pic" - (received from Dr. G. Tavakilian - MNHN); 1 male with 4 labels: 1) "Amasia / 11.IV.911", 2) "*Dorcadion* / *sericatum* / v. *macropus* / Kr.", 3) "ex coll. / A. Menshikov", 4) "*Dorcadion* / *macropus* Kr. / N. Plavilstshikov det." - ZMM; female with 2 labels: 1) "Amasia / Stauding", 2) "*Dorcadion* / *sericatum* Kryn / v. *atripes* Reitt. / N.Plavilstshikov det." - ZMM; female with 3 labels: 1) "Amasia / As. min.", 2) "*D. caucasicum*" / "perroudi Pic", 3) "*cinerarium* / perroudi / Pic / 35" - ZMM; female

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with 2 labels: 1) “Amasia”, 2) “*Dorcadion / caucasicum* Küst / a. *sericatulum* Kr. / N. Plavilstshikov det.” - ZMM; female with 2 labels: 1) “Amasia.”, 2) “*D. caucasicum / m. atripes* Rtt. / N. Plavilstshikov det.” - ZMM; 1 male with 2 labels: 1) “Amasia”, 2) “*Dorcadion / caucasicum / macropus / Kr. / det. Breuning*” - MD; 1 male with 4 labels and white small scrap of paper: 1) “Amasia / Stgr. 1897”, 2) “*Dorcadion v. atripes*”, 3) “к. G. Siversa” [in Russian], 4) “var. *atripes* Reitt.” - ZIN; 1 female with 3 labels and white small scrap of paper: 1) “Amasia / Stgr. 1897”, 2) “*Dorcadion v. atripes*”, 3) “к. G. Siversa” - ZIN.

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) micans* Thomson, 1867**

Figs 12-16

Dorcadion micans Thomson, 1867: 61 - “Armenien” - Anatolia; Kraatz, 1873: 101.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) micans, Lazarev, 2009: 198-199 - “Many *Dorcadion* populations from Turkey and North Iran (originally described as different species) were wrongly regarded as different forms of *D. cinerarium* (*D. micans* Thomson, 1867, *D. sericatulum* Kraatz, 1873, *D. macropus* Kraatz, 1873), as *D. cinerarium* does not penetrate already in Transcaucasia”; 2012: ; Danilevsky, 2010: 250, part. - Turkey; Özdikmen, 2010: 448, part. - “Type loc.: Turkey: Bolkar Mts.”; 2012: 769 - ““Armenia” (clearly N Turkey)”.

Type locality. Central Anatolia, provinces: Eskisehir, Ankara, Kirikkale, Aksaray.

“Armenia” sensu Thomson (1867) is about whole Anatolia. For example *Dorcadion weyersi* Thomson, 1867 (= *weyersi* Fairmaire, 1866) was also described from “Armenia”, but known from west Anatolia only.

The type of the species is not known. Certain authors accepted the type locality in rather different areas from Taurus Mts (Özdikmen, 2010: 448 - “Bolkar Mts”) to “clearly N Turkey” (Özdikmen, 2012: 769).

Here the type locality is preliminary accepted as Central Anatolia (provinces: Eskisehir, Ankara, Kirikkale, Aksaray), because of coincidence of local populations with original description and good preservation of traditional valid names.

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Small beetles, with totally red antennae and legs (including tarsi); lateral pronotal spines very short, rounded; white pronotal line very narrow or indistinct; elytra regularly oval, with fine punctation, in males without dense pubescence, more or less glabrous with white sutural line accompanied by black stripes; body length in males: 9.0-12 mm, in females: 10.5-14.0 mm; body width in males: 3.3-4.3 mm, in females: 4.3-5.7 mm.

Distribution. Turkey; the species is definitely known from Eskisehir (Bos-Dagh) and Ankara (Yenice) provinces. It was also recorded from Amasia.

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) micans micans* Thomson, 1867**

Figs 12-15

Dorcadion micans Thomson, 1867: 61 - "Armenien" - Anatolia; Kraatz, 1873: 101.

Dorcadion sericatum Kraatz, 1873: 98 - "Caucasus".

Dorcadion micans, Kraatz, 1873: 101, part. (one of several variations: "Mas var. *antennis totis rufis*")

Dorcadion sericatum [sensu Krynicky] var. *corallicornis* Pic, 1904: 4 ("12-14 mm") - "Angora", "Amasia" [according to Pic (1904) the same form was described by Kraatz (1873) as a part of *D. micans* Thoms.]

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) cinerarium m. *sericatum*, Breuning, 1962: 363 - "Ankara, Brussa".

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) cinerarium m. *corallicorne* Breuning, 1962: 362 - "Amasia, Ankara".

Type locality. Central Anatolia (see above).

Male elytra mostly glabrous, shining; pronotum with scattered fine punctation; white pronotal line indistinct; lateral elytral stripes very narrow covering epipleurae only; humeral elytral stripes in males totally absent; body length in males: 9-12 mm, in females: 10.5-14 mm; body width in males: 3.2-4.3 mm, in females: 4.3-5.7 mm.

Distribution. Turkey; Ankara and Amasia provinces.

Materials. 1 male, lectotype of *D. sericatum* Kraatz, 1873 (present designation on the base of photo by L.Behne) with 5 labels: 1) "Caucas. / Heynem.", 2) "*sericatum* / Kraatz / Caucas. Mniczech", 3) "coll. Kraatz", 4) "Syntypus" [red], 5) "Plavilstshikov

/ revid 1937” - SDEI; 1 female [a photo was sent to me by L.Behne as a syntype of *D. sericatum* Kraatz] with 3 labels: 1) “*causicum*” / [not readable] / “Cauc., Mnisz”, 2) “coll. Kraatz”, 3) “Syntypus” [red] - SDEI [the female is not designated as a paralectotype of *sericatum* Kraatz because of lacking of corresponding identification label by Kraatz]; 11 males, 1 female, “Angora. / Asia Min. / V.M. Duchon” - ZMM; 2 males, Turkey, Ankara, prov. Yenice (about 39°22'28"N, 32°2'25"E), 1000 m, 5.5.1989, W.Heinz - MD; 1 male, “Amasia / 1888 Korb.” - ZIN; 1 male, “130 Lederer 1868 Amasia / *D. causicum*” - ZIN; 1 male, “930 *D. causicum* / Amasia / Lederer 1868” - ZIN; 1 female (autochromal), “Amasia / 1888 г. Korb.” - ZIN; 1 female (autochromal), Ankara, 11.4.35 Filippov - ZIN.

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) micans subvestitum* K. Daniel, 1900, stat. n.**

Fig. 16

Dorcadion subvestitum K. Daniel, 1900: 140 - “Asia minor” (“9-11 mm”).

Dorcadion sericatum var. *subreductum* Pic, 1942: 2 - “Asie M^{re}”.

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) subvestitum, Breuning, 1962 : 280 - “Bos Dagh bei Oedemisch” [in fact Bos Dagh in Eskisehir - regular Breuning’s mistake, who also recorded “*D. mniszehi* ssp. *semibrunneum* Pic” from Oedemisch, while it is known from Eskisehir].

Type locality. Turkey: Bos-Dagh, Eskisehir- on the base of old series with label: “Asia-minor, Bos-Dagh, v. Bodemeyer”, which totally coincides with the original description.

The subspecies is characterized by unique scattered irregular pubescence of male elytra (females autochromal); pronotum with dense moderately small punctation; white pronotal line distinct; lateral elytral stripes rather wide covering about half of curved elytral margin; poor rudiments of humeral elytral stripes also present; body length in males: 9.0-10.0 mm, in females: 10.5-12.0 mm; body width in males: 3.3-3.6 mm, in females: 4.7-5.0 mm.

Materials. 1 male, 1 female, Klein-Asien, Boz-Dagh [Eskisehir, about 39°54'18"N, 30°35'36"E], v. Bodemeyer - ZMM; 1 male with same label - ZIN; 3 males, with same label - MD; 1 male with 3 labels 1) “Klein-Asien, Boz-Dagh, v. Bodemeyer”, 2) “400”,

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3) “*Dorcadion / subvestitum* Dn. / *D. Sumacov* det.” - ZIN; 2 males, “v. Bodemeyer, Asia-minor, Boz-Dagh” - ZMM; 2 females, “Eski-Şehr, Asia Minor” - ZMM.

Distribution. Turkey; Eskisehir (Bos-Dagh).

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) kartalense sp. n.

Fig. 17

Type locality. Turkey: Eskisehir prov., Kartal Gecidi.

Only three males known; small beetles with red femora and tibiae, but black tarsi; antennae black with red 1st joint; thoracic tubercles larger than in *D. micans*, but also obtuse; prothorax relatively smooth with fine scattered punctation (more smooth in the holotype), without white stripe; male elytra glabrous, smooth, without longitudinal furrows; without humeral stripes; sutural white stripe is accompanied black stripes; fine elytral punctation is slightly longitudinally arranged; length in males: 9.6-11.0 mm, width: 3.7-4.1 mm.

Materials. Holotype, males, Eskisehir prov., Kartal Gecidi, 20.5.2000, P. Bialooki - MD; 2 paratypes: 2 males, with same label - MD

Distribution. Turkey, Central Anatolia, Eskisehir prov., Kartal Gecidi, 39°54'14"N, 31°26'5"E.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) paramicans sp. n.

Figs 18-27

The species must be partly sympatric with *D. micans*, though no evidences of joined localities available; body of middle size; antennae from black with red 1st joint to about totally red; prothorax with wide rounded lateral tubercles, pronotum shining with fine scattered punctation, sometimes pronotal punctation can be bigger and denser; pronotal white setae line usually totally absent in males or represented by small anterior and posterior rudiments; elytra regularly oval, with white sutural stripes, which are fringed in males by narrow black stripes; elytra in males glabrous, shining, without humeral stripes; marginal stripes cover epipleurae only; elytral male punctation usually very fine, nearly indistinct with several scattered

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punctures along poorly developed furrows, elytral carinae nearly obliterated; females usually autochromal with dense pronotal and elytral pubescence; dark female pubescence bright-brown, pale elytral and pronotal stripes grayish; humeral elytral and dorsal pale stripes can be rather contrast or less distinct, often with black spots; legs are totally bright-red; body length in males: 10.4-12.3 mm, width: 3.9-4.4 mm; body length in females: 12.0-13.2 mm, width: 4.8-5.2 mm

Distribution. Turkey, Central Anatolia, nine localities are definitely known in 4 provinces: Ankara, Kirikkale, Çorum and Yozgat.

Three subspecies are separated.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) paramicans paramicans ssp. n.
Figs 18-23

Type locality. Turkey: Çorum prov., 14 km N Alaca, 1100 m.

Pronotum usually with small dense punctation; antennae black with red 1st joint, or slightly reddish; elytra usually with fine irregular sculpture; females are androchromal or autochromal; body length in males: 8.5-11.4 mm, width: 3.1-3.9 mm; body length in females: 10.3-10.8 mm, width: 4.1-4.9 mm

Materials. Holotype, male, Çorum prov., 14 km N Alaca, 1100 m, 07.04.1977, W.Heinz - ML; 27 paratypes: 2 males, 3 females, with same label - WH; 2 males, 2 females Çorum prov., 12 km W Alaca, 1100 m, 29.04.1996, Heinz leg. - WH; 4 males, 1 female, Çorum, Alaca, 1200 m, 06.05.2000, D. Obydov leg. - MD; 5 males, 6 females, Yozgat prov., Eymir, Sorgun distr, 1700 m, 14.5.2000, D. Obydov leg. - MD; 1 male, 1 female, Yozgat prov., Basiamac, 820 m, 5.5.1996, S. Kadlec leg. - MD.

Distribution. Turkey; south of Çorum prov. and north Yozgat prov.: Çorum prov., 14 km N Alaca, 1100m, about 40°17'20"N, 34°47'38"E; Çorum prov., 12 km W Alaca, 1100 m, about 40°09'32"N, 34°42'53"E; Çorum prov., Alaca, 1200 m, about 40°4'10"N, 35°6'11"E; Yozgat prov., Eymir, Sorgun distr, 1700 m, about 40°4'26"N, 35°13'14"E; Yozgat prov., Basiamac, 820m, about 40°9'30"N, 35°24'20"E.

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Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) paramicans keskiense ssp. n.

Figs 24-25

Type locality. Turkey: Kirikkale prov., Keskin, 1400 m.

Pronotum usually with sparser fine punctation; antennae totally dark-reddish; elytra usually with fine scattered punctation; both available females autochromal; body length in males: 11.0-11.5 mm, width: 3.9-4.1 mm; body length in females: 11.6-11.8 mm, width: 4.7-4.9 mm.

Materials. Holotype, male, Kirikkale prov., Keskin, 1400 m, 7.4.1976, W. Heinz - ML; 3 paratypes: 1 male, 2 females with same label - ML, WH.

Distribution. Turkey, Central Anatolia, Kirikkale prov., Keskin environs, 1400 m, about 39°43'1"N, 33°37'15"E.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) paramicans kalechikense ssp. n.

Figs 26-27

Type locality. Turkey: Ankara prov., Kozayagi NW Kalecik, 1200 m.

Pronotum very smooth, often with indistinct punctation; antennae totally bright-red; elytra often partly wrinkled with distinct punctation; all 3 available females autochromal; body length in males: 10.2-11.7 mm, width: 4.2-4.4 mm; body length in females: 11.5-12.8 mm, width: 5.0-5.3 mm

Materials. Holotype, male, Ankara prov., Kozayagi NW Kalecik, 1200 m, 1.V.1976, W. Heinz - MD; 12 paratypes: 9 males, 3 females, with same label - MD.

Distribution. Turkey, Central Anatolia, Ankara prov., Kozayagi NW Kalecik, 1200 m, 40°7'59"N, 33°21'24"E.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) menradi aksarayense ssp. n.

Figs 28-30

Type locality. Turkey: E Aksaray prov., Gukunkaya, 1200 m

The taxon is close to *Dorcadion menradi menradi* Holzschuh, 1989 described from two rather distant localities in "Prov. Maraş": Afşin environs and "zwischen Elbistan und Matatya". A good series

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of the nominative subspecies is available in my disposal from about second locality of the original description (12 males, 12 females, Ozbek koyu, 27km E Elbistan, Kahramanmaras, 15.4.1992, Heinz leg. - about 38°12'47"N, 37°28'13"E, 1400 m).

The new taxon is similar to the nominative subspecies by body size, body shape, color of legs (red), elytral and pronotal pubescence (glabrous in males with white sutural stripe accompanied by black pubescence), presence of two forms of females (autochromal and androchromal). It strongly differs by usually coarse elytral punctation arranged in longitudinal rows along shallow furrows more distinct in females; antennae in the nominative subspecies usually totally rather dark, or black with red 1st joint dark, but very rare several first joints are dark-red; antennae in the new subspecies could be also totally rather dark, but often several first joints are light-red, sometimes only 1st joint is red; females usually autochromal, brown with distinct pale dorsal, elytral lines; one female from the type series is androchromal (glabrous), one is transitional with very fine scattered elytral pubescence; body length in males: 11.0-12.0 mm, width: 3.9-4.3 mm; body length in females: 11.2-12.3 mm, width: 4.8-5.3 mm.

Materials. Holotype, male, E Aksaray prov., Gukunkaya, 1200 m, 24.4.1981, W.Heinz - ML; 9 paratypes: 4 males, 5 females with same label - ML, WH; 1 female, Konya prov., Dinek, 1100m, 26.4.1996, W.Heinz - MD.

Distribution. Turkey, Central Anatolia: E Aksaray prov., Gukunkaya, 1200 m, about 38°21'57"N, 34° 9'58"E; Konya prov., Dinek, 1100 m, about 37°19'20"N, 2°38'58"E.

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) tokatense* Pic, 1901**

Figs 31-33

Dorcadion impressicolle var. *tokatense* Pic, 1901: 12 [a single female] - "Tokat"

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) cinerarium m. *micans*, Breuning, 1962: 362, part. (= var. *tokatense* Pic).

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) micans micans, Danilevsky, 2010: 250, part. (= *tokatense* Pic).

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) niksarensense Bernhauer & Peks, 2013: 327 - "Türkei, 11 km n. Niksar, 1100 m", Tokat prov.

Type locality. Turkey, Tokat prov. - according to the original description.

The taxon was described on the base of a single androchromal female, which made difficult the exact identification of the populations from Tokat province. Never the less I accept as typical two populations from the nearest Tokat environs. All males with glabrous shining elytra, with narrow white sutural and marginal stripes similar to *D. micans* Kr., but pronotal punctation much more distinct and regular, thoracic lateral tubercles more angulated, elytral furrows obliterated without big punctures; body length in males: 9.5-10.4 mm, width: 3.6-4.4 mm; body length in females: 10.3-11.0 mm, width: 4.2-4.8 mm.

Another taxon of same group was described from Tokat province: *D. (C.) niksarensis* Bernhauer & Peks, 2013, but unfortunately the authors compared in with *D. cinerarium* (Fabricius, 1787) [with unknown origin] and not mentioned *Dorcadion tokatense* Pic, 1901. In fact the females of *D. niksarensis* agree good enough with the original description of the holotype female of *D. tokatense* Pic, as well as a glabrous female from near Tokat. In general type series of *D. niksarensis* differs from the specimens of *D. tokatense* from near Tokat by several small characters: elytra with distinct longitudinal furrows, pronotum less punctated, autochromal females absent. So, I accept here the taxon from near Niksar as *Dorcadion tokatense niksarensis* Bernhauer & Peks, 2013, **stat. nov.**, and the populations from near Tokat as *Dorcadion tokatense tokatense* Pic, 1901.

Materials. 3 males, 2 females, Turkey, Tokat, Deviçi Dag, 8 km E Kizililnis Pass, 1200 m, (about 40°12'2"N, 36°31'22"E), 25.4.2008, M.Nabozhenko leg. - MD; 1 male, Turkey, Tokat env. (about 40°22'41"N, 36°33'21"E), 900 m, F.Kleinfeld - MD.

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) pittinorum* Pesarini & Sabbadini, 1999**
Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) pittinorum Pesarini & Sabbadini, 1999: 48
- "10 km ad Est di Çorum".
Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) pittinorum, Danilevsky, 2010: 251.

Type locality. Turkey; 10 km eastwards Çorum (about 1200m, 40°36'7"N, 35°4'E).

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Pronotum and elytra in males and autochromal females always glabrous strongly shining, with very fine scattered indistinct punctation, with white sutural line accompanied by black stripes; pronotum in males and autochromal females without white line; females can be autochromal with dense elytral pubescence; lateral thoracic spines short, obtuse; lateral elytral stripes very narrow, rarefied, covering epipleurae only; humeral elytral stripes in males totally absent; legs totally red; antennae partly red or black with red 1st joint; body length 9.5-12.8 mm (according to the original description); body length of available males: 10.5-13.0 mm; in available females: 11.8-13,5 mm; body width in males: 3.8-4.8 mm, in females: 4.6-5.6 mm.

Distribution. Turkey, Çorum province.

Two subspecies are recognized.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) pittinorum pittinorum
Pesarini & Sabbadini, 1999

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) pittinorum Pesarini & Sabbadini, 1999: 48
- "10 km ad Est di Çorum".

Type locality. Turkey; 10 km eastwards Çorum (about 1200 m, 40°36'7"N, 35°4'E).

The nominative subspecies differs by much more smooth lateral sides of pronotum, which often have no dots at all, or several scattered dots; humeral furrows often totally indistinct, without dots or very shallow with single dots; several basal antennal joints can be reddish; besides about all females are androchromal; according to the original description only six autochromal specimens were observed among several hundreds of females; body length 9.5-12.8 mm (according to the original description); body length of available males: 10.5-12.0 mm; in available females: 11.8-12,8 mm; body width in males: 3.8-4.4 mm, in females: 4.6-5.2 mm.

Distribution. Turkey, Çorum prov.; 10 km eastwards Çorum (Pesarini & Sabbadini, 1999), about 1200m, 40°36'7"N, 35°4'E; 9km northwards Çorum, 1150m, about 40°37'30"N, 34°55'41"E.

Materials. 2 males, each with two labels: 1) "TR vil. Corum, Çorum, 10 km NE, 2/3.V.1992, lg. Pesarini & Sabbadini"; 2) *D. pittinorum*

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nob. des C. Pesarini & A. Sabbadini 1995 PARATYPUS ♂ - MD; 1 female with two labels: 1) "Turchia, 750m [definitely wrong data, as all localities in the region are higher than 1000m], Çorum 10km NE, 17.IV.1990, lg. R. & L. Pittino", 2) D. pittinorum nob. des C. Pesarini & A. Sabbadini 1995 PARATYPUS ♀ - MD; 3 males, 3 females, TR, ca 9km nord Çorum 1150 m, 7.4.1977, W. Heinz leg. - WH.

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) pittinorum paraullrichi* ssp. n.**

Figs 34-35

Type locality. Turkey; prov. Çorum, Sülüklü, north-eastwards Mecitözü, 950m, about 40°34'52"N, 35°19'53"E.

Lateral sides of pronotum with big distinct punctation, which can be rather dense (holotype); humeral furrows distinct, with several dots; antennae black with red 1st joint;; besides all available females autochromal with densely pubescent elytra; dark elytral pubescence light-brown; humeral and external dorsal elytral stripes grayish; body length in males: 12.0-12.8 mm; in females: 12.2-13,5 mm; body width in males: 4.6-4.8 mm, in females: 5.4-5.6 mm.

Distribution. Turkey, prov. Çorum; two localities known: Sülüklü, north-eastwards Mecitözü, 950 m, about 40°34'52"N, 35°19'53"E and Mecitözü, 700 m, about 40°32'52"N, 35°22'50"E.

Materials. Holotype, male with a label: "TR (Çorum), Sülüklü, 950 m, ne Mecitözü, 29.IV.1996, W.Heinz leg. - ML; 4 paratypes; 1 male, 2 females with same label - WH; 1 female with 2 labels: 1) "Anatolia bor. Heinz leg.", 2) "Mecitözü, ca. 700m (Çorum), 17.IV.1977 - WH.

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) rarepunctatum* sp. n.**

Figs 36-37

Type locality. Turkey; prov. Kayseri, about 4km westwards Sariz, 1700 m, about 38°28'52"N, 36°28'29"E

New species is characterized by scattered big and distinct elytral punctation; antennae black with red 1st joint, which can be very dark, nearly black; prothorax with short, obtuse lateral tubercles; pronotum totally glabrous or posteriorly with poor traces

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of central white line, shining, with deep scattered regular punctation; central longitudinal depression can be totally absent; elytra usually with very distinct regular scattered punctation, strongly shining; elytral furrows indistinct; sutural white line accompanied by very narrow black stripes; legs totally red; all females androchromal; body length in males: 9.3-11.3 mm; in females: 9.7-12,5 mm; body width in males: 3.5-4.1 mm, in females: 4.4-5.4 mm.

Distribution. Turkey; two localities known: prov. Kayseri, about 4 km westwards Sariz, 1700 m, about 38°28'52"N, 36°28'29"E and prov. Sivas, Gökpinar b. Gürün,, 1400 m, about 38°43'18"N, 37°16'22"E.

Materials. Holotype, male with label: Turkey; prov. Kayseri, W Sariz, 1700 m, 25.4.1989, W.Heinz leg. - ML; 35 paratypes; 17 males, 8 females with same label - WH; 5 males, 5 females with label: "TR (Sivas), Gökpinar b. Gürün,, 1400 m, 22.IV.1992, W.Heinz leg. - WH.

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) susheriense* Breuning, 1970, stat. nov.**

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) sinopense susheriense Breuning, 1970: 97 - "sur le Col, au sud de Susheri [Suşehri], 1700 m alt."

Dorcadion cinerarium susheriense, Braun, 1979: 81 - "Anmerkung des Verfassers: Die Arbeit bezieht sich nicht auf *D. sinopense* ssp. *susheriense*, sondern auf *D. cinerarium* ssp. *susheriense* (handschriftliche Korrektur Breuning's in meinem Separatum)".

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) micans susheriense, Danilevsky, 2010: 250.

According to the original description the attribution of the taxon to *D. sinopense* was just a misprint by Breuning, as he wrote: "comme m. *caucasicum* Kuest.", so he regarded it as *D. cinerarium* F., that was accepted by Braun (1979).

The placement of the taxon inside *D. micans* by Danilevsky (2010) was just a formal action, based on my opinion (Lazarev, 2012) that *D. cinerarium* absent in Turkey.

I was not able to study the types of *D. sinopense susheriense* Breuning, 1970. In fact the area of *D. micans* strongly distant from the locality of the taxon - Suşehri (40°10'N, 38°05'E). According to the original description the taxon is close to *D. cinerarium* (as "m. *caucasicum*"), but characterized by rather smooth pronotum and

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elytra, and so similar to Caucasian high mountain group of species around *D. sisianense* Lazarev, 2009 and *D. megriense* Lazarev, 2009). Now it must be accepted as a species: *D. (C.) susheriense* Breuning, 1970, **stat. nov.**

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) subdivisum* Breuning, 1955, stat. nov.**

Figs 38-40

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) divisum subdivisum Breuning, 1955: 263 - "Ankara".

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) divisum subdivisum, Danilevsky, 2010: 246.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) catenatum subdivisum, Danilevsky, 2012: 115.

The species has no connection with *catenatum* [= *divisum*]-group of species because of normal small regular punctation of pronotum with very fine white central stripe, while in the taxons close to *D. catenatum* Waltl, 1838 [= *divisum* Germar, 1839] pronotum usually has central longitudinal furrow surrounded by velvety black stripes and very strong big punctation laterally; lateral thoracic tubercle are rounded in *D. subdivisum*, while in species close to *D. catenatum* lateral thoracic tubercles look like short spines. Besides the areas of all species of *catenatum* [*divisum*]-group are situated in the west part of Anatolia, while *D. subdivisum* is known from Ankara prov. only. The species looks very similar to Armenian *D. daratshitshagi* Suvorov, 1915 with same elytral design, that is about same as in males of *D. sareptanum* Kraatz, 1873.

Materials. 7 males [length: 9.5-12.0 mm], 1 female [length: 11.1 mm], Ankara prov., 2km W Hirfanli (about 39°16'27"N, 33°30'28"E) 950 m, 24.4.1992, Heinz leg. - ML & MD.

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Figs 1-4. *Dorcadion macropus* Kraatz, 1873:

1 - lectotype (present designation) of *D. macropus* Kraatz, 1873, male, “Amasia” - SDEI; 2 - paralectotype (present designation) of *D. macropus* Kraatz, 1873, male [“Amasia”] - SDEI; 3 - paralectotype (present designation) of *D. macropus* Kraatz, 1873, male [“Amasia”] - MNHN; 4 - paralectotype labels of *D. macropus* Kraatz, 1873, male [“Amasia”] - MNHN.

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Figs 5-8. *Dorcadion macropus* Kraatz, 1873:

5 - holotype of *D. macropus* var. *obscurans* Pic, 1892, female, "Amasia" - MNHN; 6 - holotype labels of *D. macropus* var. *obscurans* Pic, 1892, female, "Amasia" - MNHN; 7 - holotype of *D. sericatum* var. *atripes* Reitter, 1900, female, "Amasia" - HNHM; 8 - holotype labels of *D. sericatum* var. *atripes* Reitter, 1900 - HNHM.

Figs 9-11. *Dorcadion macropus* Kraatz, 1873:
9 - syntype of *D. subobesum* Pic, 1942, female, 14.2 mm, ["Amasia"] - MNHN; 10 - syntype labels of *D. subobesum* Pic, 1942, female ["Amasia"] - MNHN; 11 - male, "Amasia".
Figs 12-13. *Dorcadion micans micans* Thomson, 1867:
12 - lectotype (present designation) of *D. sericatum* Kraatz, 1873, male, ["Caucasus"] - SDEI; 13 - female (designated as a "syntype" *D. sericatum* Kraatz, 1873 by SDEI).

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Figs 14-15. *Dorcadion micans micans* Thomson, 1867:

14-15 - males, Turkey, Ankara, prov. Yenice (about 39°22'28"N, 32°2'25"E), 1000 m, 5.5.1989, W.Heinz.

Fig 16. *Dorcadion micans subvestitum* K. Daniel, 1900 - male, Anatolia, Boz-Dagh, v. Bodemeyer.

Fig. 17. *Dorcadion kartalense* **sp. n.** - holotype, male, Eskisehir prov., Kartal Gecidi, 20.5.2000, P. Bialooki

Figs. 18-22. *Dorcadion paramicans paramicans* **ssp. n.:**

18 - holotype, male, Çorum prov., 14 km N Alaca 1700 m, 7.4.1977, Heinz leg.; 19-20 - paratypes, males with same label; 21-22 - paratypes, females with same label.

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Fig 23. *Dorcadion paramicans paramicans* ssp. n.:

18 - paratypes, female, Çorum prov., 14 km N Alaca 1700 m, 7.4.1977, Heinz leg.

Figs. 24-25. *Dorcadion paramicans keskiense* ssp. n.:

24 - holotype, male, Kirikkale prov., Keskin, 1400 m, 7.4.1976, W. Heinz leg.; 25 - paratype, female with same label.

Figs 26-27. *Dorcadion paramicans kalechikense* ssp. n.:

26 - holotype, male, Ankara prov., Kozayagi NW Kalecik, 1200 m, 1.V.1976, W. Heinz; 27 - paratype, female with same label.

Figs 28-30. *Dorcadion menradi aksarayense* ssp. n.:

28 - holotype, male, E Aksaray prov., Gukunkaya, 1200 m, 24.4.1981, W.Heinz; 29-30 - paratypes, females with same label.

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Figs 31-33. *Dorcadion tokatense* Pic, 1901:

31 - male, Tokat, Deviçi Dag, 8 km E Kizililnis Pass, 1200 m, 25.4.2008, M.Nabozhenko leg.; 32-33 - females with same label.

Fig. 34-35. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) pittinorum paraullrichi* **ssp. n.:**

34 - holotype, male, Çorum, Sülüklü, 950m, ne Mecitözü, 29.IV.1996, W.Heinz leg.; 35 - paratype, female with same label.

Fig. 36-37. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) rarepunctatum* **sp. n.:**

36 - holotype, male, prov. Kayseri, W Sariz, 1700 m, 25.4.1989, W.Heinz leg.; 37 - paratype, female with same label.

Fig. 38-40. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) subdivisum* **stat. n.:**

38-39 - males, Ankara prov., 2 km W Hirfanli, 950 m, 24.4.1992, W.Heinz leg.; 40 - female with same label.

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